

Three-point hydrogen bondings of carboxyl group in recognition of carboxylic acid and amino acid with designed synthetic receptors[†]

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The binding of carboxylic acids and amino acids have been reported with a series of designed synthetic receptors. The three-point binding of carboxylic acids (with receptors 2-4) has been utilised to bind acetylglutamate with receptor 6.

Host-guest chemistry to date is based primarily on binding interactions which involve weak noncovalent forces. Molecule to molecule interactions form the basis of specific recognition, reaction, transport and regulation which occur in biological systems¹. Hydrogen bonding, in this respect, as a weak directional force plays a key role in molecular recognition². In general, greater the number of hydrogen bonds contributed by the receptor, stronger is the complex formed with the guest³. The development of synthetic receptors of defined architecture having multiple hydrogen bonding sites for complementary steric match of the guest into the cavity of the receptor is thus of considerable importance. Synthetic receptors for peptides⁴ and amino acid derivatives⁵ are of prime importance due to the intermolecular interactions involving small molecule with the peptide backbone in biological system.

We report here a series of flexible and semirigid receptors for the binding studies of carboxylic acid and also amino acid employing three-point hydrogen bondings for recogni-

tion of its carboxylic acid moiety.

Results and Discussion

Previously we reported⁶ the synthesis of flexible receptor 2 and a comparative binding study on the two-point (with the simple receptor 1) versus three-point hydrogen bondings (with receptor 2) for monocarboxylic acids. The binding experiments⁶ with the receptor 2 show an increase in the binding constant value with the aliphatic monocarboxylic acids compared to the aromatic acids. The three-point hydrogen bondings with the carboxyl group have further been extended for the recognition of an amino acid with the receptors 5 and 6. The new receptors 3 and 4 along with the receptors 1⁷ and 2⁶ for binding studies of carboxylic acids and also the new receptors 5 and 6 for amino acids are shown in Fig. 1. Their mode of complexation is delineated in Figs. 2 and 3.

Our previous⁶ receptor 2 has a long methylene chain in the pendant aliphatic amide moiety. In the receptor 3, we

Fig. 1

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

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Fig. 2. Complexation mode of different receptors and dicarboxylic acids

have replaced the long methylene chain by a adamantyl group, a compact aliphatic framework containing four chair forms of cyclohexane with all the bridgehead hydrogen atoms in equatorial disposition with respect to each of the rings. The energy minimised^{8a} structures of the respective 1 : 1 complex of receptor 2 with some aliphatic acids, e.g. acetic, propanoic and myristic acids show the formation of three-point hydrogen bonds involving carboxyl group with pyridine ring nitrogen, pyridine amide-NH and aliphatic amide-NH (Fig. 4). The binding study of 3 with benzoic acid shows that both the amide protons ($\Delta\delta_{\text{pyridine}} = 1.74$, $\Delta\delta_{\text{adamantylamide}} = 0.53$ ppm) are involved in the formation of a 1 : 1 complex ($K_a = 1.75 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$) with three-point

to convert it to the unionised form having free carboxyl and amino group although there was a chance to make six-membered cyclic hydrogen bonds involving amino hydrogens and naphthyridine nitrogens as indicated in Fig. 3.

Then acetyl glycine was chosen as a better guest and we changed the design to the semirigid receptor 6 to utilise simple hetero bis-amide receptor having isophthaloyl spacer for binding of carboxylic acid moiety and the pendant furan ring to participate in hydrogen bonding with the amide proton. In the 1 : 1 complex of the receptor 6 and acetyl glycine ($K_a = 3.10 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$), the downfield chemical shift changes of pyridine amide as well as of furfuryl amide by 0.65 and 1.05 ppm, respectively, suggest the formation of three-point

Fig. 3

hydrogen bondings. We then formulated the design of receptor 4 for complexation with dicarboxylic acids based on two three-point hydrogen bonds (total six hydrogen bonds) as indicated in Fig. 2. However, the too flexible methylene spacer in 4 did not improve the dicarboxylic acid binding (K_a remains similar as $2 \times 10^2 M^{-1}$ with adipic acid as with monocarboxylic acid). This shows that the degree of flexibility in the spacer-design is an important consideration in effective complexation of dicarboxylic acids through multiple hydrogen bonding sites. To implement the concept of the three-point organisation of carboxylic acid group, we have designed and synthesised the receptors 5 and 6 for amino acid recognition. The receptor 5 was initially designed and synthesised to bind free amino acid (e.g. glycine). But due to the zwitterionic nature of amino acid and its notorious insolubility in CDCl_3 , the complexation was very weak

hydrogen bondings of carboxyl group of acetyl glycine involving both pyridine amide and furfuryl amide. However, the weak basicity of furan oxygen of receptor 6 causes a small downfield shift of glycineamide NH ($\Delta\delta = 0.10$ ppm) during complexation.

The synthesis^{8b} of receptors 3, 4, 5 and 6 are shown in Scheme 1. The coupling of the corresponding different amines by high dilution with isophthaloyl chloride afforded 3 and 6. The receptor 4 was synthesised (Scheme 1) by coupling of adipoyl chloride with the amine that was obtained by coupling of 2-amino-2-methylpyridine with 3-nitrobenzoyl chloride and its subsequent reduction under H_2 atmosphere in the presence of Pd/C.

The receptor 5 was prepared by coupling the monolithio salt of 2,7-dimethyl-1,8-naphthyridine⁹ with 2-*N*-acetyl-

Fig. 4. Energy minimised structures showing hydrogen bond distance and E_{\min} of 1 : 1 complexes of (a) **2** with acetic acid, (b) **2** with propanoic acid, (c) **2** with myristic acid.

amino-6-bromomethylpyridine¹⁰.

In conclusion, we have been able to show the binding of acetyl glycine by the use of three-point hydrogen bondings with carboxyl group (as we have used in the case of simple carboxylic acid recognition) as well as by formation of hydrogen bond of NH of acetyl amino group with furan oxygen. Exploration of the concept of three-point organisation of carboxylic acid group for the effective complexation of dicarboxylic acids (as reported in receptor **4**) need, therefore, the incorporation of a rigid spacer flanking the three-point binding motifs for each carboxyl group. This work, in

progress, will be reported in due course. We are also trying to improve the binding of amino acid by changing the furan moiety of receptor **6** by thiophene or more basic pyridine ring for formation of stronger hydrogen bond with NH of acetyl glycine.

Experimental

M.p.s. were recorded on a Toshniwal hot-coil stage apparatus and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker spectrometer (200 MHz) and IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer-833 spectrophotometer. Energy minimised calculations were done by PCMODEL for Windows (Serena Software-1993) using standard constants.

1-[[6-Methylpyrid-2-yl]amino]carbonyl]-3-[[adamantylamino]carbonyl]benzene (3) : To a solution of isophthaloyl diacidchloride (0.33 g, 1.65 mmol) in methylene chloride (50 ml), 2-amino-6-methylpyridine (0.18 g, 1.65 mmol) and adamantylamine (0.25 g, 1.65 mmol) in methylene chloride (75 ml each) were added by high dilution procedure. After usual work up, the purification was done by 4 : 1 (CHCl₃ : EtOAc) solution to give the pure product (0.34 g, 53%), m.p. 220°; ¹H NMR (200 MHz) δ 8.73 (1H, s, pyr-NH), 8.27 (1H, s, isophth-2H), 8.22 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, pyr-3H), 8.01 (2H, d of d, *J* 8, 2 Hz, isophth-4,6H), 7.66 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, isophth-5H), 7.56 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, pyr-4H), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, pyr-5H), 5.95 (1H, s, ada-NH), 2.61 (3H, s), 2.14 (6H, s), 1.73 (3H, s), 1.62 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (50 MHz) δ 165.36, 164.71, 156.94, 150.51, 138.65, 136.74, 134.45, 130.62, 129.37, 129.02, 125.14, 119.53, 110.85, 52.59, 41.58, 36.29, 29.45; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3300, 3286, 2914, 2856, 1666, 1634, 1533, 1448 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 389 (M⁺), 346, 332, 282, 239, 212, 170, 135.

1,4-Bis[1-[[6-methylpyrid-2-yl]amino]carbonyl]-3-aminobenzene]carbonyl]butane (4): 2-Amino-6-methylpyridine was coupled with 3-nitrobenzoyl chloride to obtain 1-[[6-methylpyrid-2-yl]amino]carbonyl]-3-nitrobenzene which was reduced to the corresponding amine by hydrogenation in presence of Pd/C under H₂ atmosphere. The crude amine (0.19 g, 0.84 mmol) was then coupled with adipoyl chloride (0.06 ml, 0.42 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ in presence of triethylamine (0.3 ml) under N₂ atmosphere. Usual work up and final purification on column chromatography using methanol-chloroform (2 : 98) as eluant afforded the title compound (0.25 g, 53%), m.p. 131–132°; ¹H NMR (200 MHz) δ 9.24 (2H, s, pyr-NH), 8.95 (2H, s), 8.21 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.03 (2H, s, benz-NH), 7.79 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.70–7.60 (4H, m), 7.42 (2H, t, *J* 8 Hz), 6.90 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 2.46 (6H, s), 2.41 (4H, bm), 1.68 (4H, bs).

2-(N-Acetylamino-6-pyridylethyl)-7-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine (5): To a stirred solution of 2,7-dimethyl-1,8-naphthyridine (100 mg, 0.63 mmol) in dry THF at –78°, *n*-BuLi (0.2 ml, 1.5 mmol) was added dropwise under nitrogen atmosphere. Then the solution was stirred at –78° for 0.5 h until red colour persisted. Then a solution of 2-*N*-acetylamino-6-bromomethylpyridine (288 mg, 1.26 mmol) in THF was added dropwise. The red colour gradually disappeared and finally a yellow colour appeared. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo* and water was added to the mixture. The aqueous layer was extracted with chloroform and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After evaporation of the solvent, the crude product was purified by PTLC using EtOAc in CHCl₃ (20%) to afford the title compound (0.08 mg, 42%), m.p. 145°; ¹H NMR (200 MHz) δ 8.30 (1H, s, NH), 8.00 (2H d of d, *J* 8, 2 Hz), 7.57 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz), 7.34–7.23 (3H, m), 6.91 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 3.42–3.41 (4H, m), 2.79 (3H, s), 2.20 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR (50 MHz) δ 168.6, 164.9, 162.8, 159.3, 155.5, 150.7, 149.8, 138.7, 136.6, 122.3, 121.7, 119.0, 116.3, 111.2, 38.4, 37.0, 25.4, 24.6; ν_{\max} 3265, 3058, 2927, 2857, 2354, 1679, 1604, 1538, 1450 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 307 (M⁺), 117, 59.

1-[[6-Methylpyrid-2-yl]amino]carbonyl]-3[[furfuryl]amino]carbonyl]benzene (6): The compound was obtained by high dilution coupling of 2-furfurylamine and 2-amino-6-methylpyridine with isophthaloyl diacid chloride (1 : 1 : 1 by mole ratio) in dry CH₂Cl₂. The pure product (46% yield) was obtained as a light yellow semi-solid after purification by column chromatography using benzene : ethyl acetate mixture (3 : 1) as the eluant : ¹H NMR (200 MHz) δ 8.98 (1H, s, pyr-NH), 8.32 (1H, s), 8.10 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 8.01 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.59 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz), 7.48 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz),

7.31–7.28 (1H, br), 7.20 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz, fur-NH), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 6.29–6.22 (2H, m), 4.58 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 2.39 (3H, s).

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